

**Mathematical Modelling of intra-tumour
heterogeneity: the role of survival-proliferation
trade-offs in cancer cell quiescence.**

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Abstract

Quiescent cancer cells are in tumours. This thesis investigates the mechanisms driving cancer cells into a quiescent state, particularly under hypoxic conditions, using mathematical modelling to explore survival-proliferation trade-offs. It contrasts the simplistic phenomenological approach with a more detailed model accounting for cell damage dynamics and quiescence regulation. The findings reveal a tendency for quiescence in hypoxic environments, offering insights for future research on treatment strategies and cancer cell resistance.

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1 Introduction

Cancer continues to be a significant public health issue with a substantial global impact on mortality rates. The disease's complexity and its varied manifestations across different populations and regions highlight the ongoing challenge in combating this major cause of death worldwide. From a microscopic point of view, cancer is a hereditary disease caused by changes in the genes that control the function of cells, especially those that control cell growth and division.

In recent decades, our understanding of cancer has evolved. While cancer has been originally viewed solely as a disease of uncontrolled cell growth, it is now considered as a dynamic ecosystem [1], shaped by mutation and selection acting on cells within a tissue. This perspective emphasizes the significance of tumour heterogeneity in cancer development and progression [2]. Intra-tumour heterogeneity is the result of both genetic and epigenetic variations between cancer cells that arise and are selected for within the unique environmental conditions of the tumour [3]. For example, rapidly proliferating and quiescent cells can coexist within the same tumour. The heterogeneity is, therefore, not just limited to genetic diversity but also extends to phenotypic variability, such as differences in metabolic activity, proliferation rate, and response to environmental stressors. There is therefore a need to understand the interplay between mutation, natural selection and the tumour microenvironment (TME) in shaping the emergence and distribution of cancer cells with heterogeneous traits within tumours.

Understanding life history theory [4] has been proposed as a framework to understand the diversity of cell phenotypes observed in tumours [1]. This theory emphasises the crucial role of trade-offs in shaping evolutionary phenotypes, as organisms often cannot maximise all their functions simultaneously [5]. For example, cancer may be exposed to trade-offs between maximizing proliferation and maximizing survival. This leads to the critical role of DNA damage repair, particularly in proliferating tissues where damage can accumulate if not adequately repaired due to insufficient expression of DNA repair genes. This accumulation can lead to premature ageing in non-proliferating cells [6]. As shown in the schematic in Figure 1, cells have developed anti-cancer regulatory mechanisms to prevent the proliferation of damaged cells. A normal (*i.e.*, non-cancerous) cell, upon DNA damage, may arrest the cell-cycle and enter into a quiescent state to attempt repair, leading to cell death if unsuccessful (see Figure 1a). In contrast, cancer cells acquire the ability to hijack regulatory mechanisms allowing them to continue replicating despite damage. As a result, they have higher proliferation rates than normal cells from the tissue of origin but also increased risk of accumulating mutations and genomic instability (see Figure 1b). This difference gives cancer

cells an evolutionary advantage over normal cells, allowing for rapid and uncontrolled proliferation. However, this can also make cancer cells more sensitive to external sources of damage due to their lowered ability to repair damage. This is the rationale behind several common therapies, such as radiotherapy and PARP inhibitors [7].

Figure 1: As cells proliferate they naturally acquire damage, due to random error in DNA replication and/or external stresses. Cells have developed mechanisms to prevent the replication of damaged cells via detection and repair of damage, when possible. In cancer, damaged cells can escape detection and continue proliferating despite the accumulation of damage. This is represented in the schematic above by the additional green arrow in the right panel.

In terms of external stresses, cancer progression is significantly influenced by hypoxia, a condition characterized by pathologically low oxygen levels within tissues. This state often emerges due to the excessive proliferation of cancer cells, leading to an oxygen supply insufficient for the demand. Hypoxia can have profound effects on cancer development, notably impacting DNA repair mechanisms and genomic stability, key factors in the evolution of cancerous tissues [8]. Moreover, cancer cells must adeptly regulate their gene expression to survive in these low-oxygen environments while also maintaining a balance with their rate of proliferation, highlighting the pivotal role of oxygen in both cellular health and the progression of cancer [9].

In the realm of cancer research, mathematical models serve as powerful tools, providing quantitative frameworks to interpret complex biological phenomena and bridging the gap between *in vitro* and *in vivo* complexities of TME [10]. In this the-

sis, we are interested in using mathematical modelling to study how proliferation-survival trade-offs contribute to shaping intra-tumour heterogeneity. To do so, we have developed and analysed a hierarchy of increasingly complex mathematical models that elucidate how evolution and trade-offs can facilitate the coexistence of rapidly and slowly proliferating cancer cells.

In Chapter 2, we start with a simple phenomenological model of tumour growth in the presence of proliferation-survival trade-offs. Our initial model involves a system of two Ordinary Differential Equations (ODE) describing the evolution of the numerical of proliferative and quiescent cancer cells. In Section 2.1 to Section 2.4, we explore the predictions of this simple model combining analytical and numerical results. The model predicts that the total population of cancer cells eventually grows exponentially (in the absence of competition) at a rate dictated by the dominant eigenvalue of the ODE system. In this context, we can easily define the fitness of the population in terms of the model parameter as this is given by the dominant eigenvalue. In Section 2.5, we update the defined fitness function to account phenomenologically for trade-offs between proliferation and survival. In Section 2.5.1 to Section 2.5.3 we study the properties of the proposed fitness function and its prediction of optimal strategy changes in the presence of proliferation-survival trade-offs. Section 2.5.4 will delve deeper into how oxygen concentrations drive the selection of survival strategies in cancer cells.

In Chapter 3, we developed a mechanistic model for proliferation-survival trade-offs that directly account for their relation to the regulation of DNA repair in cancer. To this end, we derive a system containing two damaged-structured compartments and one well-mixed compartment for the system containing damage repair with a single repair delay to investigate the influence of repair time on growth dynamics. Then the original calculation of the Partial Differential Equation (PDE) solved by *methods of characteristics* is shown to derive the final Delayed Differential Equations (DDE) for the growth dynamics with damage repair. Then we will make a comparison between these two models to conclude the similar overall growth dynamics but quite different trade-offs shown as a result. Our approach involves the use of a combination of analytical original calculations to uncover insights into the strategies governing cell proliferation and survival.

We conclude in Chapter 4 by summarising our key results and outlining possible extensions of the presented work.

2 A phenomenological model of proliferation-survival trade-offs in cancer

Here we develop the first simple model that allows tumour cells to transition between two states - proliferation and quiescence. In Section 2.1 to Section 2.4, we solve ODE to show the effects of heterogeneity of tumours in growth dynamics. In Section 2.5, we introduce trade-offs with a new death rate which is inversely proportional to the transition rate from proliferation to quiescence. Also by implementing numerically, we analysed the population composition in different environmental conditions (oxygen level effects).

2.1 A two-compartment model of tumour growth

Figure 2: Schematic representation of our two-compartment model of tumour growth, see Eqs. (1). The two compartments N_P and N_Q represent respectively proliferative and quiescent cells within the tumour. We assume that the transition rate between the two compartments at rates $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ and $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$. Cells in the proliferative compartment proliferate at a rate α but are also sensitive to death (indicated by the empty set, \emptyset) which occurs at a rate μ_P .

By considering the population of tumour growth accounting for heterogeneity in cancer cell proliferation, we assume that the population of cancer cells is made up of two cell types: a proliferative phenotype and a transiently arrested (i.e., quiescent phenotype). We denote with N_P and N_Q respectively the number of proliferation and quiescent cells, where the total number of cells N can be represented as $N = N_P + N_Q$. the model is governed by a set of ordinary differential equations that describe the transitions between proliferating and quiescent states, as well as the rates of birth and death for each state. These equations are grounded in the principles of population dynamics and reflect the biological processes underlying tumour growth. To model the population change with the conservation equation: growth equals "birth" minus "deaths" [11], where the evolution of the number of

cells in each compartment is dictated by three key processes: proliferation, death and phenotypic transitions.

As illustrated in Figure 2, we assume that cells in the proliferative compartment have inflow the number of cells from self-proliferation at rate α and the phenotypic switch from quiescence state to proliferation at rate $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, also the outflow to the quiescence state at rate $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ and the number of death proliferation cells at rate μ_P . Quiescent cells instead are protected from cell death and can repair accumulated damage, which was introduced in detail in Chapter 1. Hence we assume the death rate of cells in the quiescent state is 0, and the only dynamic that happens in the quiescence state is the phenotypic switches between the two states. The Equations (1a)-(1c) as being analogous to a Gyllenber-Webb model [11] but neglecting cell competition (*i.e.*, we do not need to think about the limit of transition rate ranges).

Under the above assumption, the evolution of the number of cells in each model compartment is described by the following system of coupled-linear Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs):

$$\frac{dN_P}{dt} = \alpha N_P + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} N_Q - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} N_P - \mu_P N_P, \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{dN_Q}{dt} = \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} N_P - \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} N_Q, \quad (1b)$$

with initial conditions,

$$N_P(0) = n_p > 0, \quad N_Q(0) = n_q \geq 0. \quad (1c)$$

Due to mechanisms we have, we assume $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}, \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}, \mu_P, \alpha > 0$. All rates are measured in units of 1/day which captures the time-scale associated with cancer cell doubling time (≈ 1 day) [9]. Moreover, to aid the analysis, we introduce $\bar{\alpha} = \alpha - \mu_P$.

2.2 Asymptotic growth dynamics

Next, we are interested in investigating how model parameters affect the asymptotic population growth dynamics. From Eqs. (1a)-(1b), we obtained two equations that are linear and can therefore be solved explicitly via a 2×2 homogeneous linear system:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}(t)}{dt} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{N} \iff \frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} N_P \\ N_Q \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} & \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} \\ \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} & -\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} N_P \\ N_Q \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

Note that since we assume $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}, \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} > 0$, \mathbf{A} is a Metzler matrix (*i.e.*, it has all off-diagonal terms non-negative), and, hence, the equations define a positive dynamical system, which refers to any type of dynamical system (*e.g.* deterministic/stochastic linear/non-linear systems of ODEs and/or PDEs with or without delays). Here we focus on the linear system of ODEs, where the solution of $N(t)$ will be used to model the dynamics of a growing population of cells. Therefore, the Metzler matrix guarantees that equations preserve the positivity of solutions, which means the dominant eigenvalue of the linear system would be real. Lemma 1 summarizes the results on the asymptotic dynamics of Eqs. (1a)-(1b).

Lemma 1. *Suppose the following conditions are satisfied:*

$$\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}, \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} > 0, \quad \alpha > 0, \quad \mu_P > 0, \quad N_P(0) = n_p > 0, \quad N_Q(0) = n_q \geq 0$$

and denoted by λ_+ the dominating exponent of Eqn. (4), we then have:

- When $\bar{\alpha} > \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, $\lambda_+ > 0$ and $\lambda_- < 0$, as t goes to infinity, $\mathbf{N}(t)$ eventually growth exponentially at rate λ_+ . The population of cells would grow to infinity.
- When $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} > \bar{\alpha} > 0$, $\lambda_+ > \lambda_- > 0$, as t goes to infinity, $\mathbf{N}(t)$ is proportional to $e^{\lambda_+ t}$ as λ_+ is the larger one to determine the growth rate.
- When $\bar{\alpha} < 0$, $\lambda_- < \lambda_+ < 0$, as t is large. The number of cells is decaying towards and $\mathbf{N}(t)$ towards zero at rate λ_+ .
- The critical case is when the $\bar{\alpha} = 0$, then $\lambda_+ = 0, \lambda_- = 0$. In this case, the population remains constant $\mathbf{N}(t)$ with every t .

Proof. From the characteristic equation $\det(\mathbf{A} - \lambda I) = 0$, we have:

$$\det \begin{vmatrix} \bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} - \lambda & \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} \\ \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} & -\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (3)$$

So that we obtain the eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} :

$$\lambda_{\pm} = \frac{-(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \bar{\alpha}) \pm \sqrt{(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \bar{\alpha})^2 + 4\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}\bar{\alpha}}}{2}. \quad (4)$$

Here the eigenvalues λ_{\pm} are real since the discriminant

$$\Delta = \sqrt{(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \bar{\alpha})^2 + 4\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}\bar{\alpha}} \quad (5)$$

are positive, where $4\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}\bar{\alpha}$ are non-negative in the context of a biological system as $\bar{\alpha}$ and $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ are always greater than 0. Next, we find the eigenvector \mathbf{v}_+ corresponding to λ_+ by solving:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{0} &= (\mathbf{A} - \lambda_+ \mathbf{I})\mathbf{v}_+ \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{(\bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}) - \Delta}{2} & \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} \\ \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} & \frac{(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} - \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \bar{\alpha}) - \Delta}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \end{pmatrix} \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{(\bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}) - \Delta}{2} v_1 + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} v_2 \\ \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} v_1 - \frac{(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} - \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \bar{\alpha}) - \Delta}{2} v_2 \end{pmatrix} \\
\implies v_2 &= \frac{(\bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}) - \Delta}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}} v_1 \\
\implies \mathbf{v} &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{(\bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}) - \Delta}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}} \end{pmatrix} v_1
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly we can compute the eigenvector \mathbf{v}_- associated with λ_- :

$$\mathbf{v}_- = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} - \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \bar{\alpha}) + \Delta}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}} \end{pmatrix} v_1$$

Now we have the matrix \mathbf{C} that diagonalized \mathbf{A} such that:

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ \frac{(\bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}) - \Delta}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}} & \frac{(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} - \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \bar{\alpha}) + \Delta}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}} \end{pmatrix},$$

where the diagonal matrix

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{C}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_+ & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_- \end{pmatrix}.$$

So the general solution of the decoupled equation

$$\frac{d\mathbf{z}}{dt} = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{z}$$

will be

$$\mathbf{z} = \begin{pmatrix} c_1 e^{\lambda_+ t} \\ c_2 e^{\lambda_- t} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence we obtain the general solution of $\frac{d\mathbf{N}}{dt}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{N}(t) &= \mathbf{C}\mathbf{z} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ \frac{(\bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}) - \Delta}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}} & \frac{(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} - \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \bar{\alpha}) + \Delta}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_1 e^{\lambda_+ t} \\ c_2 e^{\lambda_- t} \end{pmatrix} \\ &= c_1 e^{\lambda_+ t} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{(\bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}) - \Delta}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}} \end{pmatrix} + c_2 e^{\lambda_- t} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} - \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \bar{\alpha}) + \Delta}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}} \end{pmatrix}.\end{aligned}$$

Since we only consider the long-time behaviour of the total population of cells, at $t \rightarrow \infty$, as λ_+ would dominate in all regimes shown in 1, so we have

$$\mathbf{N}(t) \approx c_1 e^{\lambda_+ t} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{(\bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}) - \Delta}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} N_P \\ N_Q \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where $c_1 = n_P$. We now obtained the general solution of $\mathbf{N}(t)$, which provided us the behaviour shown in Lemma 1 as time becomes very large (i.e. as $t \rightarrow \infty$). \square

To show the composition of population distribution for proliferating and quiescence cells separately, we compute analytically the asymptotic fraction of $\frac{N_P}{N}$ and $\frac{N_Q}{N}$:

$$\frac{N_P}{N} = \frac{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} + (\bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}) - \Delta} \quad (7a)$$

$$\frac{N_Q}{N} = \frac{(\bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}) - \Delta}{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} + (\bar{\alpha} - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}) - \Delta} \quad (7b)$$

The analytical exploration of our model reveals the long-term behaviour of the cell population dynamics under various transition rates between proliferating (N_P) and quiescent (N_Q) states. Specifically, by focusing on the dominant eigenvalue, λ_+ , we derive an approximate solution for $\mathbf{N}(t)$ as t approaches infinity. This simplification is crucial for understanding the system's behaviour in the asymptotic limit, allowing us to analytically compute the fractions of proliferating and quiescent cells in the total population. The resulting expressions for $\frac{N_P}{N}$ and $\frac{N_Q}{N}$ provide insight into the distribution of cell states over time, emphasizing the impact of transition rates and growth dynamics on the population composition. With these analytical foundations in place, we transition to numerically simulating the model to elucidate the dynamics under specific scenarios further.

(a) Logarithms of Numerical vs Analytical N for $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \gg \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$

(b) Composition numerical graph of $\frac{N_P}{N}$ and $\frac{N_Q}{N}$ for $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \gg \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$

(c) Logarithms of Numerical vs Analytical N for $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$

(d) Composition numerical graph of $\frac{N_P}{N}$ and $\frac{N_Q}{N}$ for $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$

(e) Logarithms of Numerical vs Analytical N for $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \ll \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$

(f) Composition numerical graph of $\frac{N_P}{N}$ and $\frac{N_Q}{N}$ for $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \ll \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$

Figure 3: The parameters for numerical solutions: $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 0.1$, where large $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = 100\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ (in Figure 3(a)-3(b)), small $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = 0.01\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ (in Figure 3e-3f), $\bar{\alpha} = 1$, with initial conditions $n_p = 100$ and $n_q = 50$. For Figure 3a, the y-axis is scaled differently from 0 to 2.26, since the proliferating population grows relatively slowly in this case.

2.3 Results from numerical simulations

To complement our analytical findings and better understand how different transition rates $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}, \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ could deliver different population dynamics between two phenotypic states, we plotted graphs in Figure 3, where we consider three different scenarios of (top row) $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \gg \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, (middle row) $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, (bottom row) $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \ll \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$. Note that we here consider only the case $\bar{\alpha} > 0$, for which we predict the population eventually reaches a regime of exponential growth (rather than decay). Utilizing MATLAB 'ode23' solver, we directly compare the outcomes of numerical simulations with our analytical predictions. This approach validates our model and provides a deeper understanding of the conditions under which the cell population tends to increase, guided by the positivity of λ_+ as highlighted in Lemma 1.

Interestingly, we find that the model can capture a range of different behaviours. Contrasting with the other two scenarios, Figures 3a and 3b demonstrate different dynamics. When $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \gg \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, indicating a low transition rate from quiescence to proliferation, all cells eventually arrest in a quiescent state (see Figure 3a). Consequently, the dominating growth rate λ_+ approaches zero, leading to linear growth of the cell population (see Figure 3b). Moreover, the change in the composition of the population leads to an overall slow-proliferating population.

As shown in Figures 3c and 3d, we can find parameter regimes in which the model predicts the persistent coexistence of proliferating and quiescent cells. Despite the decreasing trend, quiescent cells never completely vanish, indicating a continuous, albeit small, presence within the population. Figure 3c depicts the population dynamics when the transition rates between proliferating and quiescent states are equal (*i.e.*, $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$). In this scenario, the total cell population increases exponentially, aligning with our prior analysis. This exponential growth is less pronounced compared to scenario $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \ll \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ (illustrated in Figures 3e to 3f), **as a higher number of cells** transitioning from proliferating to quiescent states leads to increased resistance to death.

2.4 Parameters sweeps

To investigate the trade-offs between proliferation and quiescence cells, we are interested in exploring how model parameters affect the asymptotic population growth dynamics. As we have seen in Sections 2.2 to 2.3 and Lemma 1, the model can capture a range of behaviour depending on the choice of the model parameters. We explore the behaviour of the eigenvalue λ_+ is always dominating the asymptotic population of growth dynamics for all situations by sweeping the parameters $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$

(a) $\bar{\alpha} = 1$, with dashed line indicate the contour $\lambda_+ = 0.5$

(b) $\bar{\alpha} = -1$, with dashed line indicate the contour $\lambda_+ = -0.5$

Figure 4: Change in asymptotic growth rate λ_+ as a function of parameters $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ and $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, illustrating the system's behaviour under different interaction strengths between populations N_P and N_Q .

and $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$. So we study how the asymptotic population growth rate depends on the phenotypic transition rates, $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ and $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, with $\bar{\alpha} = 1$ (shown in Figure 4a) and $\bar{\alpha} = -1$ (shown in Figure 4b) respectively.

Looking at Figure 4a, we see a surface plot that for $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \ll \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, λ_+ approaches the maximum possible proliferation rate $\bar{\alpha} = 1$. In other words, more cells are transitioning from quiescence to proliferating, which leads to an activated proliferation and death rate in the dynamical system. For $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \gg \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, λ_+ tends to 0. In this regime, cells accumulate in the quiescent compartment resulting in the overall population growing extremely slowly approaching a regime of linear rather than exponential growth. Then the population eventually reaches a regime of linear growth (*i.e.*, $N \propto t$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$).

Figure 4b presents an opposite trend to Figure 4a, where λ_+ is maximized when $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \gg \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$. In this scenario, proliferative cells are more likely to die than successfully proliferate (*i.e.*, $\bar{\alpha} = -1 < 0$). Hence, transitioning to quiescent is an advantageous strategy as it protects cells from otherwise certain death. Biologically, this corresponds to a regime in which cells are exposed to a toxic environment, such as hypoxia [8], as we discussed in Chapter 1. Keeping this simple trade-off analysis in mind, we could introduce a more complex term including new transition rates in the next section.

2.5 Introducing proliferation-survival trade-offs in our model

Tumours evolve via mutations [12], which enables cells to explore a range of possible behaviours. According to the standard view of cancer, to be arrested in a state of cancerous growth, a cell has to “achieve” two goals. One, enter proliferative growth, and second, escape quiescence [13]. However, this view can not explain the presence of quiescent cells within *in vivo* tumours (see Chapter 1).

Evolutionary forces drive cancer cells towards strategies that maximise their proliferation. However, since evolutionary time-scales are slow, they can penalise mutation yielding instantaneous bursts in cell proliferation if this is not sustainable, *i.e.*, if it can lead to population extinction due to accumulation of damage and stress in the long run. What condition is sustainable further depends on the local environment cells are exposed to. Here we are interested in investigating spatial heterogeneity in the tumour environment, and how the selection of mutation shapes cell behaviour. To this end, we assume that cells have been exposed to evolutionary pressure for a long time and they have converged to the optimal cell strategy that enables them to maximise their fitness.

In evolutionary game theory and ecology, the concept of fitness includes not

only the ability of cells to proliferate but also their capacity to survive [14]. This implies that, through the process of evolution, parameter values tend to evolve toward an optimal point that maximizes fitness, which is mathematically represented as λ_+ . This convergence towards λ_+ signifies the selection of traits that enhance both survival and reproductive success.

In the previous section, we explored how the population growth rate λ_+ depends on the transition rate parameters $(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}, \beta_{Q \rightarrow P})$. In doing so, we have assumed that all these two parameters change independently. However, we expect cells to be constrained in how they can explore the transition rate parameters space. When $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ approaches zero, cells proliferate for a long time without entering quiescence. This implies that they do not take time to repair any damage accumulated during the proliferation state, which increases their likelihood of dying. In other words, if cells do not arrest to proliferate sufficiently, their death rate will be higher as they will on average have accumulated more damage. In contrast, as $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ becomes larger, more cells are entering quiescence to prevent damage, which decreases the cells' death rate. Hence, this can be modelled by assuming that μ_P is a decreasing function of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$. Here we consider the simplest case in which μ_P is inversely proportional (up to a constant) to $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$:

$$\mu_P = \bar{\mu} + \frac{\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}}, \quad (8)$$

$\bar{\mu}$ and γ are positive constants, where γ represents the strength of cost of delaying the transition to quiescence and $\bar{\mu}$ acts as a foundational death rate upon which the effects of transitions (and their associated repair or damage accumulation mechanisms) are added.

By substituting Eqn. (8) into Eqn. (4), we find that the updated λ_+ has the form:

$$\lambda_+(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}) = \frac{1}{2}(-A + \sqrt{A^2 + B}), \quad (9)$$

where we denote

$$\begin{cases} A(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}) := \left(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \alpha + \bar{\mu} + \frac{\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}} \right), \\ B(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}) := 4\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} \left(\alpha - \bar{\mu} - \frac{\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}} \right) \end{cases}$$

Intuitively, we assume cancer cells evolved to maximise their proliferation rate so that the optimal value of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ they can obtain is the one that maximises λ_+ . In

other words, we could prove Eqs. (10a and 10b) by Lemma 2.

$$\frac{d\lambda_+}{d\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}} = 0, \quad (10a)$$

$$\frac{d^2\lambda_+}{d\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}^2} < 0. \quad (10b)$$

2.5.1 Existence and uniqueness of optimal strategy in the presence of proliferation-survival trade-offs: analytical results

To obtain the summarized results in Lemma 2, we first study analytically the existence and uniqueness of an optimal strategy for cells, *i.e.*, existence and uniqueness of a global maximum for the fitness function $\lambda_+(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q})$.

Lemma 2. *For each $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, provided that $\alpha - \bar{\mu} > 0$, there exists a unique optimizer $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}^* > 0$ that maximises the population growth rate $\lambda_+(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q})$.*

Proof. We start by studying the sign of λ_+ for values of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} > 0$. We start by looking at the points in which the curve $\lambda_+(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q})$ crosses the zero axis. We find that there exists only one root for the function $\lambda_+(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}) = 0$ that we denote by $\beta_{cr} > 0$:

$$\lambda_+(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}) = 0 \implies B = 0 \implies \beta_{cr} = \frac{\gamma}{\alpha - \bar{\mu}}.$$

Taking the first derivative of Eqn. (9) with respect to $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ we have that:

$$\frac{d\lambda_+}{d\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(-A' + \frac{1}{2} \frac{2AA' + B'}{\sqrt{A^2 + B}} \right), \quad (11a)$$

where

$$\begin{cases} A'(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}) = 1 - \frac{\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}^2}, \\ B'(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}) = \frac{4\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}^2}. \end{cases} \quad (11b)$$

By evaluating Eqn. (11) at the critical point $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = \beta_{cr}$, we find that:

$$\frac{d\lambda_+}{d\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}}(\beta_{cr}) = \frac{2\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}(\alpha - \bar{\mu})^3}{\gamma(\gamma + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P}(\alpha - \bar{\mu}))} \quad (12)$$

which is positive as $\alpha - \bar{\mu} > 0$. This implies that near the critical point λ_+ increases with $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ and transition from negative to positive. Given that the

curve $\lambda_+(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q})$ has a single zero for $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ we can conclude

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_+(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}) < 0, & \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \in [0, \beta_{cr}), \\ \lambda_+(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}) \geq 0, & \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \in [\beta_{cr}, \infty). \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Since we are interested in maxima of the function λ_+ , Eq. (13) implies that we only have to focus on stationary points of λ_+ located in the interval $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} > \frac{\gamma}{\alpha - \bar{\mu}}$.

Next, we show that, for $\lambda_+ > 0$ (i.e. $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} > \frac{\gamma}{\alpha - \bar{\mu}}$), there is at most one critical point exists and if it exists, it should be the maximum. From Eqn. (9), taking the first derivative and setting it to be zero:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\lambda_+}{d\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(-A' + \frac{1}{2}(A^2 + B)^{-\frac{1}{2}}(2AA' + B') \right) = 0, \\ \implies \frac{2AA' + B'}{2\sqrt{A^2 + B}} &= A' \\ \implies (A')^2 &= \frac{(2AA' + B')^2}{4(A^2 + B)} \end{aligned}$$

To show the behaviour of this critical point, we take the second derivative of λ_+ and evaluate it at the critical point:

$$\frac{d^2\lambda_+}{d\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}^2} = \frac{1}{2} \left[A'' \left(\frac{A}{\sqrt{A^2 + B}} - 1 \right) + \frac{B''}{2\sqrt{A^2 + B}} \right],$$

where

$$\begin{cases} A'' = \frac{2\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}^3} \\ B'' = -\frac{4\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}^2}. \end{cases}$$

For $\lambda_+ > 0$, which implies $B > 0$. Therefore,

$$\left(\frac{A}{\sqrt{A^2 + B}} - 1 \right) < 0, \text{ and } B'' < 0 \implies \frac{d^2\lambda_+}{d\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}^2} < 0.$$

After proving the uniqueness and maximum, we now have to show that the critical point exists for $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} > \beta_{cr}$:

$$\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} > \beta_{cr} \implies \lambda_+(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}) > 0,$$

we assume the maximum λ_+ is at infinity, so that

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_+ &= -\frac{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \alpha + \bar{\mu}}{2} \\
&\quad + \frac{\sqrt{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}^2 + 2\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}(\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \alpha + \bar{\mu})}}{2} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}}\right) \\
&= -\frac{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \alpha + \bar{\mu}}{2} \\
&\quad + \frac{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}}{2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{2(\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \alpha + \bar{\mu})}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}}} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}}\right) \\
&= -\frac{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \alpha + \bar{\mu}}{2} \\
&\quad + \frac{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}}{2} (1 + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} - \alpha + \bar{\mu}) + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}}\right) \\
&\approx \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}}\right) \rightarrow 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Proving by contradiction, there exists a unique critical point for $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} > \beta_{cr}$. \square

The presence of a unique optimal maximum point for λ_+ implies that there is a specific parameter configuration (such as certain values of $\bar{\mu}$ or γ) where cells are most efficient in their proliferation and survival. This indicates that cells can adapt to their environment and adopt strategies that maximize their fitness. Therefore, cells always have the optimal strategy to maximise their ability to proliferate and survive under spatial heterogeneity.

In the next section, we will investigate numerically how changes in parameters provide different trade-off strategies as the tumour evolves.

2.5.2 Characterising optimal strategy under proliferation-survival trade-offs: numerical results

In Figure 5, we plot the fitness function λ_+ as a function of the transition rate $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ for different values of the $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ and γ . We find that both $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ and γ influence the maximum fitness and the optimal value of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ for which such maximum fitness is achieved. Notably, I initially set the α and $\bar{\mu}$ to be the same value, which means the net proliferation rate of the proliferative cells is less than or equal to zero (≤ 0) for all $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$. This led us to a curve from negative infinity λ_+ to the optimum value approaching zero (see in Figure 5a). This is because no trade-offs

Figure 5: Plots illustrating how the fitness function λ_+ depends on the transition rate $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ for different values of the strength of proliferation-survival trade-offs γ . Results are obtained for the following values of the parameters (a) $\alpha = \bar{\mu} = 1.1$; $\gamma = \{0.01, 0.1\}$; (b) $\bar{\mu} = 0.1$; $\alpha = 1.1$; $\gamma = \{0.01, 0.1\}$.

exist in this regime between proliferation and survival. Since this is not realistic, we consider here after the regime $\alpha > \bar{\mu}$ (see Figure 5b).

By looking at the results in Figure 5b, we find that there is indeed an optimal strategy for each given set of $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ and γ values, which matches our analysis in Section 2.5.1. Furthermore, for both γ values, as $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ increases, the peak of λ_+ shifts to the right, which means a higher $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ is needed to achieve the maximum fitness. However, there are fewer variations of optimal λ_+ at $\gamma = 0.01$ with different values of $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, which represents the death rate of proliferation cells is less influenced by how quickly cells are transitioning to quiescence so that the cells will maintain proliferating longer since they are not experiencing as much damage. Conversely, cells would prefer to stay in quiescence and avoid damage once the cost of selection is higher $\gamma = 0.1$.

Additionally, the presence of a cost for delaying the transition to quiescence γ shifts the entire curve downwards and is more flattening, indicating a decrease in the maximum growth rate λ_+ for all values of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$. The dashed lines $\gamma = 0.1$ are always below their solid line $\gamma = 0.01$ counterparts for the same $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, illustrating the negative impact of a higher γ on the fitness λ_+ . Therefore we can conclude that the optimal strategy of trade-offs between proliferation and quiescence depends on the balance between different transition rates and costs. Next, we would analyse the heterogeneity in trade-offs due to these complexities by varying parameters and observing the outcomes.

2.5.3 The influence of damage repair on proliferation-survival trade-offs

In this section, we will explore more on how changes in $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ influence the optimal cell strategy for the cell to maximise their fitness under proliferation-survival trade-offs. We recall that $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ is inversely proportional to the average time a cell spends in the quiescence state. This is therefore related to how quickly cancer cells can repair any damage and stress they have accumulated. By studying how λ_+ depends on $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$, we aim to understand how inhibition of damage repair decreases in $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ affects cell adaption.

We start by exploring analytically how the optimal $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ is in the extreme case: when $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} \approx 0$ (slow damage repair) for which we can find an explicit solution. This information will be useful when estimating the optimal $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ numerically. By using the analytical expression of λ_+ from Eqn. (9) and substituting $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 0$,

we find that the fitness function λ_+ reduces to:

$$\lambda_+ = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} - \alpha + \bar{\mu} + \frac{\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left| \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} - \alpha + \bar{\mu} + \frac{\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}} \right| \quad (14)$$

and its derivative with respect to $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ to

$$\frac{d\lambda_+}{d\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}} = \begin{cases} 0, & \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} - \alpha + \bar{\mu} + \frac{\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}} \geq 0, \\ -1 + \frac{\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}^2}, & \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} - \alpha + \bar{\mu} + \frac{\gamma}{\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}} < 0, \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where $|\cdot|$ in Eq. (14) indicates the absolute value of the function. We have therefore one of two scenarios

- 1) if $2\sqrt{\gamma} - \alpha + \bar{\mu} > 0$, then any choice of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} > 0$ is optimal, according to our definition, and it eventually yields to the complete arrest of cancer growth, as $\lambda_+ \equiv 0$ independently of the choice of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$;
- 2) if $2\sqrt{\gamma} - \alpha + \bar{\mu} < 0$, then there exists an optimal strategy $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = \sqrt{\lambda}$ corresponding to a maximal proliferation rate of $\lambda_+ = -(2\sqrt{\gamma} - \alpha + \bar{\mu})$. Hence we have that for increasing γ the optimal value of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ increases but results in a decrease in the maximum **proliferation** rate. This is in line with the trend observed in Figure 5b for values of $\beta_{QP} > 0$.

To find the implicit optimized value of λ_+ , we use ‘**fsolve**’ in MATLAB applied to Eqn. (9). We estimate the derivative of λ_+ using the central finite differences method with the initial guess to be $\sqrt{\gamma}$ (based on our previous analysis). From Eqn. (8), since γ influences the function significantly when $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ is small, starting the search at $\sqrt{\gamma}$ avoids the extremes where γ either dominates (when $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ is too small) or is negligible (when $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ is too large). We imply the same parameters setting $\alpha = 1.1$, $\gamma = 0.01, 0.1$, $\bar{\mu} = 0.1$, illustrated in Figure 6.

In Figure 6, the graph depicts the optimized transition rate $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ as a function of the rate at which cells transition from quiescence to proliferation, $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$. A positive correlation is observed, where an increase in $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ leads to a rise in the optimized $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$, indicating that the ability of cells to leave quiescence enhances their propensity to enter it. The graph also demonstrates that with a lower cost of delaying quiescence ($\gamma = 0.01$), the optimized $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ is lower than that for a higher cost ($\gamma = 0.1$). This suggests a strategic adaptation in the transition rates to optimize fitness, taking into account the penalty for prolonging the proliferative state.

However, the model presents an unexpected behaviour in different cost-of-death conditions, where a preference for quiescence would be presumed, yet it suggests a

Figure 6: We plot the value of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ that optimises the fitness function, Eqn. (9) as a function of $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$. All other parameters are set as in Figure 5b.

predilection for proliferation. This anomaly might reveal limitations in the model's current form, hinting at the need for a more complex model to account for the intricate dynamics of cellular responses under stress. The effect of different γ values on transition rates indicates that higher cell mortality—or a lower cost of death, equivalent to a lower γ —prompts a less frequent shift from proliferating to quiescent states to maximize fitness. It is anticipated that forthcoming models, to be introduced in Chapter 4, will rectify these incongruities and provide a more accurate representation of cellular strategies in diverse environmental conditions.

2.5.4 Changes in population composition and cell behaviour between normoxic and hypoxic region of the tumour

In the previous section, we discussed the variety of heterogeneity in terms of the selection of different mutations. In particular, our model predicts that decreasing $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ can help cells cope with reduced ability to repair DNA damage (*i.e.*, decrease in $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$). This could reflect an ideal strategy for cells to cope with environmental conditions, such as hypoxia [8]—abnormally low oxygen levels, which is known to reduce DNA repair ability of cells.

Here we study how adaptation of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ to changes in $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ affects the balance

(a) Composition of $\frac{N_P}{N}$ and $\frac{N_Q}{N}$ when $\gamma = 0.01$ (i.e. when the cost of delaying the transition to quiescence is smaller), and $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ represent hypoxia ($\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 0.025$) and normoxia ($\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 10$). We have explicit solutions of optimized $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = 0.1015$ in hypoxia and optimized $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = 0.3409$ in normoxia

(b) Composition of $\frac{N_P}{N}$ and $\frac{N_Q}{N}$ when $\gamma = 0.1$ (i.e. when the cost of delaying the transition to quiescence is smaller), and $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ represent hypoxia ($\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 0.025$) and normoxia ($\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 10$). We have explicit solutions of optimized $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = 0.3263$ in hypoxia and optimized $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = 1.1453$ in normoxia.

Figure 7: Composition of $\frac{N_P}{N}$ and $\frac{N_Q}{N}$ in Different Oxygen Environment and Selection

between proliferative and quiescent states and whether this is sufficient to explain the observed increase in quiescent cells in the hypoxic core of tumours.

Next, we aim to provide a direct composition graph to illustrate how exactly the population of cells will transit in different conditions of $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$: (normoxia) $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 10$ and (hypoxia) $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 0.025$. Using similar techniques for Figure 3, where we change the matrix because of the new trade-offs we have. By setting again $\alpha = 1.1$, $\bar{\mu} = 0.1$ and $\gamma = 0.01$ or 0.1 , with the explicit values of optimized $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ of each value $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ and γ , we can compute the evolution of cell number in the proliferative and quiescent compartments (see insets in Figure 7).

As described above, the size of $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ represents the environmental change, especially in oxygen level change. Therefore, we can tell from the plot that in a normoxia state ($\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 10$) proliferation dominates independently of the strength of proliferation-survival tradeoffs (*i.e.*, value of γ). We note however a slight increase in the asymptotic fraction of quiescent cells at long times for a larger value of γ (Figure 7b). In line with biological observation, our model predicts normoxia as an environment conducive to growth. Conversely, when the transition rate is low ($\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 0.025$), quiescence is favoured compared to the normoxic case regardless of the strength of the tradeoffs γ . However, the asymptotic fraction of quiescent cells is significantly higher for larger values of γ (see Figure 7b). Specifically speaking, when in $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 0.025$ (*i.e.*, in hypoxia), and $\gamma = 0.1$ (the cost of the strength of trade-offs is high), much more cells would escape into quiescence compared to other environments.

When in hypoxia, an increase in $\frac{N_Q}{N}$ suggests a shift from active proliferation to a quiescence state. For example, cells enter quiescence to conserve energy, which could reduce the risk of damage that could occur during cell division. In high oxygen levels (*i.e.* normoxia), $\frac{N_P}{N}$ is high which represents a predominance of cell growth and division in the proliferation state. Cells are experiencing less stress and sufficient oxygen to remain active.

In conclusion, we do find that our model can offer an explanation for the accumulation of quiescent cells in the hypoxic region of the tumours, while in the normoxia condition cells are more likely to proliferate. In particular, our model suggests this is the result of the adaptation of cancer cells to a decreased ability to repair damage in the absence of sufficient oxygen levels.

2.6 Summary

In this section, we discussed cells' evolutionary strategies to balance between proliferating and entering quiescence, especially under challenging conditions like hypoxia. Our work emphasizes the role of survival-proliferation trade-offs in driving the evolutionary need for cells to optimize survival by strategically alternating be-

tween active growth and dormancy to lessen the risks from hostile environments.

We introduce proliferation-survival tradeoffs in a simple two-compartment model of tumour growth, which differentiates cells into a proliferation and quiescent state. Trade-offs are introduced phenomenologically in the related fitness function by prescribing a relation between cell death and the cell transition rate between proliferative and quiescent states ($\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$). This captures the dual impact of quiescence on cell fitness: it reduces fitness by lowering the rate of cell proliferation, but it can also enhance fitness by improving cell survival allowing cells the time to repair damage.

We then examine the adaptive responses of cancer cells, allowing mutations to influence $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$. Considering evolutionary time-scales, we assume cancer cells have converged towards their optimal strategy, *i.e.*, the value of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ that optimises their fitness. Through comprehensive mathematical analysis, including Lemma 2, we prove that in our model there exists a unique optimal strategy that maximizes the fitness function (here the population proliferation rate λ_+) for any value of the other model parameters that we assume are not affected by mutations.

By allowing oxygen levels to influence the duration of the quiescent phase, we use our model to gain insights into the role of proliferation-survival tradeoffs in the prevalence of quiescent cells under harsh conditions. Our results suggest that cells adjust their strategies based on oxygen availability, favouring quiescence in low-oxygen (hypoxic) environments to counteract their reduced ability to repair, and leaning towards proliferation in high-oxygen (normoxic) conditions. These findings illustrate the complex equilibrium cancer cells maintain between proliferation and dormancy, and reconcile cancer cell quiescence with the common picture of cancer evolution, according to which cancer progression is driven by selection of the fittest.

Our results however are somewhat surprising. Despite the model rightly capturing the accumulation of quiescent cells in hypoxia, it also suggests that in hypoxia, cancer cells should delay entering quiescence (*i.e.*, reduce $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$) to maximise their fitness. This suggests our modelling framework has some limitations. To test whether this is biologically relevant rather than an artefact of our modelling assumption a more detailed mechanistic model of proliferation-survival trade-offs is needed. This is discussed in the next chapter, which introduces a detailed damage-structured population model to provide a deeper mechanistic understanding of how proliferation-survival trade-offs emerge in tumours and shape their composition.

3 A mechanistic model of proliferation-survival trade-offs in cancer

In this chapter, we present a three-compartment model of tumour growth, encompassing proliferative and quiescent cells and their damage regulation. This model refines our understanding of proliferation-survival trade-offs, especially under different oxygen conditions, challenging the simpler assumptions of Chapter 2. Section 3.1 lays out the model framework, comprising two linear Partial Differential Equations coupled with an Ordinary Differential Equation. In Section 3.2, we streamline the model to a Delay Differential Equation (DDE) using the *method of characteristics*, capturing the delays in cell transition due to damage repair. Section 3.3 examines the asymptotic behaviour of tumour growth, while Section 3.4 correlates damage regulation with proliferation-survival trade-offs, elucidating how damage levels impact cell transition rates and tumour dynamics. Lastly, Section 3.5 uses numerical simulations to further explore these trade-offs and their implications in hypoxic conditions, as illustrated in Figure 10.

3.1 A damage-structured tumour growth model

As in Section 2.1, we consider a population of cancer cells that is growing in the absence of competition but explicitly accounting for the dynamics of damage regulation within cells. As illustrated in Figure 8, we divide the population of cancer cells into three compartments: two damaged-structured compartments (n_P and $n_Q^{(I)}$) and one well-mixed compartment ($N_Q^{(II)}$).

The damage level of cells is indicated by the independent variable $x \in [0, x_{max}]$, where x_{max} is a positive constant that represents the maximum damage level cells could achieve. Here the n_P compartment describes proliferative cancer cells, while $n_Q^{(I)}$ and $N_Q^{(II)}$ capture quiescent (*i.e.*, non-proliferative) cancer cells. While cells in $n_Q^{(I)}$ are damaged, cells in $N_Q^{(II)}$ have completed damage repair but have not yet restarted proliferation. Practically speaking, the damaged cells cannot be repaired instantaneously, so there is a time lag between the damaged cells entering quiescence and restarting proliferation.

As proliferative cells proliferate at a rate α , they accumulate damage at a fixed rate V_P and they die at a rate $\mu(x) \geq 0$ that increases with their level of damage (*i.e.*, $\mu'(x) \geq 0$). We assume that proliferative cells have a maximum tolerance for damage; in other words, as cells accumulate levels of damage greater than a maximum threshold x_{max} , they arrest proliferation (*i.e.*, enter quiescence)

Figure 8: Schematic representation of the proposed damage-structured population model for tumour growth.

to focus their energy on damage repair. In the model, this is captured by cells transitioning from the n_P to the $n_Q^{(I)}$ compartment. We assume that quiescent cells repair damage at a constant rate, V_R . Once quiescent cells have completed repair, they re-enter a proliferation at a rate $\beta_{II \rightarrow P}$. As in our simpler two-compartment model, we consider the death of quiescent cells to be negligible. In accordance with the schematic in Figure 8 and imposing the principle of mass balance, the time-evolution of the cell distributions $n_P(x, t)$ and $n_Q^{(I)}(x, t)$, and cell numbers $N_Q^{(II)}(t)$ are governed by the following system of differential equations (specifically, two hyperbolic PDEs for the cell distributions $n_P(x, t)$ and $n_Q^{(I)}(x, t)$, and one ODE for $N_Q^{(II)}$):

$$\frac{\partial n_P}{\partial t} + V_P \frac{\partial n_P}{\partial x} = \alpha n_P - \mu(x) n_P, \quad t > 0, x \in [0, x_{max}]. \quad (16a)$$

$$\frac{\partial n_Q^{(I)}}{\partial t} - V_R \frac{\partial n_Q^{(I)}}{\partial x} = 0, \quad t > 0, x \in [0, x_{max}], \quad (16b)$$

$$\frac{dN_Q^{(II)}}{dt} = V_R n_Q^{(I)}(0, t) - \beta_{II \rightarrow P} N_Q^{(II)}(t), \quad t > 0. \quad (16c)$$

with boundary conditions:

$$V_P n_P(0, t) = \beta_{II \rightarrow P} N_Q^{(II)}(t) := F_{in}^P(t), \quad (16d)$$

$$V_R n_Q^{(I)}(x_{max}, t) = V_P n_P(x_{max}, t) := F_{out}^Q(t). \quad (16e)$$

In Eq. (16d), the function $F_{in}^P(t) \geq 0$ indicates the influx of cells in the proliferating state. In Eq. (16e), the function $F_{out}^Q(t) \geq 0$ means the outflux of cells in the

Table 1: List of model variables and parameters. We use a.u. to indicate arbitrary units.

Parameter List		
Label	Meaning	Unit
t	normal time spent in each state	day
x	damage level	[a.u.]
$n_P = n_P(x, t)$	Distribution over the damage level x of proliferative cell	cell/[a.u.]
$n_Q^{(I)} = n_Q^{(I)}(x, t)$	Distribution over the damage level x of repairing quiescent cell	cell/[a.u.]
$N_Q^{(II)}$	The population of repaired cells in quiescence	cell
α	Proliferating rate of proliferative cell	day ⁻¹
$\mu(x)$	Rate of death for cells with damage level x	day ⁻¹
V_R	Rate of damage repair in $n_Q^{(I)}$ state	[a.u.]/day
V_P	Rate of damage accumulation	[a.u.]/day
$\beta_{II \rightarrow P}$	transition rate of repaired cells in quiescence to proliferation	day ⁻¹

proliferating state, which is the same as the influx of cells to repairing quiescent state. And initial conditions:

$$n_P(0, x) = n_P^0(x), \quad (16f)$$

$$n_Q^{(I)}(0, x) = n_Q^0(x), \quad (16g)$$

$$N_Q^{(II)}(0, x) = N_Q^0. \quad (16h)$$

Since the distribution of cells is not necessary to be negative, we assume that $n_P^0(x), n_Q^0(x) \geq 0$ for all $x \in [0, x_{max}]$. Also, the population of cells cannot be negative or infinite, so $N_Q^0 \geq 0$ and $N_P = \int_0^{x_{max}} n_P(x, t) dx < \infty$ and $N_Q^{(I)} = \int_0^{x_{max}} n_Q^{(I)}(x, t) dx < \infty$. A summary of model variables and parameters is given in Table 1.

3.2 Derivation of an equivalent delay-differential equation model of tumour growth

We show how Eqs. (16) can be reduced to a single delay-differential equation for $N_Q^{(II)}$ coupled to two explicit equations for the cell distributions $n_P(x, t)$ and

$n_Q(x, t)$.

3.2.1 Solving for $n_P(x, t)$ and $n_R(x, t)$

We solve Eqs. (16a), (16b) via the *method of characteristics*. Starting from $n_P(x, t)$, as shown in Fig. 9a, we divide the (x, t) plane into two regions: one in which the solution ($n_P(x, t)$) is determined by the initial data (i.e., Eq. (16f)), and one in which it is determined by the boundary data (i.e., Eq. (16d)).

Figure 9: Schematic illustrating the characteristic curves in the (x, t) plane for the solution of (a) $n_P(x, t)$ (see Eqs. (17)-(19)) and $n_Q^{(I)}(x, t)$ (see Eqs. (22)-(24)). In each case, the black bold line divides the plane into two distinct regions: in the purple region the solution is determined by the initial data; in the orange region, instead, the solution is determined by the boundary data. In panel (a) the bold line is $t = \frac{x}{V_P}$ divides the two regions. In panel (b) the bold line is $t = \frac{x_{max} - x}{V_R}$ defined by Eqn. (22)-(24)

We start by considering the region influenced by the initial condition (see Eqn. (16f)). In this region, we parametrise the characteristic curves via (τ, s) , where $s \in [0, x_{max}]$ corresponds to the damage level of a proliferating cell at time $t = 0$. This yields the following characteristic equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dt}{d\tau} = 1, & t(0, s) = 0, \\ \frac{dx}{d\tau} = V_P, & x(0, s) = s, \\ \frac{dn_P}{d\tau} = (\alpha - \mu(x(\tau, s)))n_P, & n_P(0, s) = n_P^0(s), \end{cases} \quad , \quad 0 \leq s \leq x_{max}. \quad (17)$$

By integrating $\frac{dt}{d\tau}$ and $\frac{dx}{d\tau}$ and using the initial condition at $t(0, s)$, $x(0, s)$ we find

the explicit form of the characteristic curves

$$\begin{cases} t(\tau, s) &= \tau, \\ x(\tau, s) &= V_P \tau + s, \end{cases}, \quad 0 \leq s \leq x_{max} \quad (18a)$$

and the governing equation for n_P along the characteristics area $t < \frac{x}{V_P}$ reads:

$$\frac{dn_P}{d\tau} = (\alpha - \mu(V_P \tau + s))n_P, \quad n_P(0, s) = n_P^0(s), \quad (18b)$$

Solving Eqs. (17) with initial condition related to n_P (i.e. Eqn. (16f) and integrating factor $I(\tau, s) = e^{-\int_0^\tau (\alpha - \mu(V_P \xi + s)) d\xi}$, we have firstly the solution governed by initial condition:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{n_P}(I(\tau, s)n_P) = 0 &\implies I(\tau, s)n_P = I(0, s)n_P(0, s), \\ &\implies n_P(\tau, s) = e^{(\alpha\tau - \int_0^\tau \mu(V_P \xi + s) d\xi)} n_P^0(s), \\ &\stackrel{\text{Eq. (18a)}}{\implies} n_P(x, t) = e^{(\alpha t - \int_0^t \mu(x + V_P(\xi - t)) d\xi)} n_P^0(x - V_P t), \\ &\stackrel{\xi^i := x + V_P(\xi - t)}{\implies} n_P(x, t) = e^{(\alpha t - \int_{x - V_P t}^x \frac{\mu(\xi^i)}{V_P} d\xi^i)} n_P^0(x - V_P t). \end{aligned}$$

In the region influenced by the boundary data (see Eqn. (16d), we parametrise the characteristic curves via (τ, s) , where $s > 0$ corresponds to the time at which a cell with damaged level x at time t entered the proliferation state. This yields the following characteristic system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dt}{d\tau} = 1, & t(0, s) = s, \\ \frac{dx}{d\tau} = V_P, & x(0, s) = 0, \\ \frac{dn_P}{d\tau} = (\alpha - \mu(V_P \tau))n_P, & n_P(0, s) = \frac{F_{in}^P(s)}{V_P}. \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Similarly, after integrating $\frac{dt}{d\tau}$ and $\frac{dx}{d\tau}$ with fixed values of $t(0, s)$, $x(0, s)$, we obtained:

$$\begin{cases} t(\tau, s) &= \tau + s, \\ x(\tau, s) &= V_P \tau, \end{cases}, \quad s \geq 0 \quad (20a)$$

and the governing equation for n_P along the characteristics area $t > \frac{x}{V_P}$ reads:

$$\frac{dn_P}{d\tau} = (\alpha - \mu(V_P \tau))n_P, \quad n_P(0, s) = \frac{F_{in}^P(s)}{V_P}, \quad (20b)$$

Then the solution affected by boundary condition:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{d}{d\tau} (e^{(\int_0^\tau -(\alpha - \mu(V_P \xi)) d\xi)} n_P) = 0, \\
& \xrightarrow{\text{Eq. (16d)}} e^{(\int_0^\tau -(\alpha - \mu(V_P \xi)) d\xi)} n_P = \frac{F_{in}^P(s)}{V_P}, \\
& \implies n_P(\tau, s) = \frac{F_{in}^P(s)}{V_P} e^{(\alpha\tau - \int_0^\tau \mu(V_P \xi) d\xi)}, \\
& \xrightarrow{\tau = \frac{x}{V_P}} n_P(x, t) = \frac{F_{in}^P(t - \frac{x}{V_P})}{V_P} e^{(\frac{\alpha x}{V_P} - \int_0^{\frac{x}{V_P}} \mu(V_P \xi) d\xi)}, \\
& \xrightarrow{\xi^i = V_P \xi} n_P(x, t) = \frac{F_{in}^P(t - \frac{x}{V_P})}{V_P} e^{\frac{\alpha x}{V_P} - \int_0^x \frac{\mu(\xi^i)}{V_P} d\xi^i}.
\end{aligned}$$

Combining the result above, we can write the distribution of proliferating cells $n_P(x, t)$:

$$n_P(x, t) = \begin{cases} \exp \left[\alpha t - \int_{x-V_P t}^x \frac{\mu(\xi)}{V_P} d\xi \right] n_P^0(x - V_P t), & t < \frac{x}{V_P}, \\ \frac{F_{in}^P(t - \frac{x}{V_P})}{V_P} \exp \left[\frac{\alpha x}{V_P} - \int_0^x \frac{\mu(\xi)}{V_P} d\xi \right] & t > \frac{x}{V_P}, \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Similarly, we can solve for $n_Q^{(I)}(x, t)$. In this case, however, the characteristics behave differently. We illustrated the phase plane in Figure 9(b). From the initial condition (16g) at $s \in [0, x_{max}]$, we obtained the characteristics equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dt}{d\tau} = 1, & t(0, s) = 0, \\ \frac{dx}{d\tau} = -V_R, & x(0, s) = s, \\ \frac{dn_R}{d\tau} = 0, & n_R(0, s) = n_R^0(s), \end{cases} \quad s \in [0, x_{max}]. \quad (22)$$

Since these characteristics can be solved by using a similar methodology as in n_P , we could omit the repetitive steps, which gives us the solution of $n_Q^{(I)}(x, t)$:

$$n_Q^{(I)}(x, t) = n_R^0(x + V_R t), \quad t < \frac{x_{max} - x}{V_R} \quad (23)$$

From the boundary condition Eqn. (16e), we have:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dt}{d\tau} = 1, & t(0, s) = s, \\ \frac{dx}{d\tau} = -V_R, & x(0, s) = x_{max}, \\ \frac{dn_R}{d\tau} = 0, & n_R(0, s) = \frac{V_P n_P(x_{max}, s)}{V_R}. \end{cases} \quad s > 0. \quad (24)$$

We obtain the solution

$$n_Q^{(I)}(x, t) = \frac{V_P}{V_R} n_P \left(x_{max}, t - \frac{x_{max} - x}{V_R} \right), \quad t > \frac{x_{max} - x}{V_R}. \quad (25)$$

Combining the result above that $n_Q^{(I)}(x, t)$ satisfies:

$$n_Q^{(I)}(x, t) = \begin{cases} n_R^0(x + V_R t), & t < \frac{x_{max} - x}{V_R}, \\ \frac{V_P}{V_R} n_P \left(x_{max}, t - \frac{x_{max} - x}{V_R} \right), & t > \frac{x_{max} - x}{V_R}. \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

3.3 A delay differential equation model of tumour growth

Having an explicit form for the distribution $n_Q^{(I)}$ (Eq. (27b)), we rewrite the system (16):

$$\frac{dN_Q^{(II)}}{dt} = F_{in}^Q(t) - \beta_{II \rightarrow P} N_Q^{(II)}(t), \quad (27a)$$

where $F_{in}^Q(t)$ is defined by

$$F_{in}^Q(t) = \begin{cases} V_R n_R^0(V_R t), & 0 < t < \tau_R, \\ V_P n_P^0(x_{max} - V_P(t - \tau_R)) e^{\alpha(t - \tau_R) - \int_{\tau_R + \tau_P - t}^{\tau_P} \mu(V_P T) dT}, & \tau_R < t < \tau_P + \tau_R, \\ \beta_{II \rightarrow P} N_Q^{(II)}(t - \tau_R - \tau_P) e^{\alpha\tau_P - U(\tau_P)}, & t > \tau_P + \tau_R. \end{cases} \quad (27b)$$

where we have introduced the two constant delays $\tau_P := \frac{x_{max}}{V_P}$ and $\tau_R := \frac{x_{max}}{V_R}$, and $U(\tau_P) = \int_0^{\tau_P} \mu(V_P T) dT$. Eq. (27b) is derived using Eqs. (21) and (26) to evaluate the influx of cells in the quiescent compartment $\beta_{II \rightarrow P} n_Q^{(I)}(0, t)$. The problem is closed by imposing initial conditions for $N_Q^{(II)}$ and the initial cell distributions n_R^0 and n_P^0 .

Interestingly, we find that the three-compartment structured population model proposed in Section 3.1 can be reduced to a single Delayed Differential Equation (DDE) for the evolution of cell numbers $N_Q^{(II)}$ and the two explicit equations (21) and (26) for the cell distribution $n_P(x, t)$ and $n_Q^{(I)}(x, t)$. For direct comparison with the simpler 2-compartment model discussed in Chapter 2, we can then estimate the total number of proliferative, $N_P(t)$ and quiescent cells, $N_Q(t)$, in the population

as

$$N_P(t) = \int_0^{x_{max}} n_P(x, t), \quad (28a)$$

$$N_Q(t) = \int_0^{x_{max}} n_Q^{(I)}(x, t)dx + N_Q^{(II)}(t). \quad (28b)$$

In the next section, we discuss the asymptotic behaviour of Eq. (27b) for long times and show how the two-compartment ODE model proposed in Section 2 can be systematically derived by looking at the long-time dynamics followed by N_P and N_Q defined by Eqs. (28).

3.3.1 Asymptotic behaviour of Eq. (27)

We start by studying the asymptotic behaviour of Eqs. (27). To help with the algebra we rewrite the DDE in the form:

$$\frac{dN_Q^{(II)}}{dt} = aN_Q^{(II)}(t - \tau_{RP}) - bN_Q^{(II)}(t), \quad (29)$$

where we denote $a := e^{\alpha\tau_P - U(\tau_P)}\beta_{II \rightarrow P}$, $b := \beta_{II \rightarrow P}$, and $\tau_{RP} = \tau_R + \tau_P$.

Since Eq. (29) is linear, with a constant delay τ_{RP} its solution can generally be expressed as a superposition of scalar functions of the form $\omega_{\Lambda_i} e^{\Lambda_i t}$, where $\Lambda_i (i = 1, 2, \dots)$ are the complex roots of the characteristic polynomial associated with Eq. (29) and n_{Λ_i} are the corresponding coefficients [9]. The characteristic polynomial can be found by substituting the form of the characteristic functions, $N_Q^{(II)}(t) = \omega e^{\Lambda t}$ into Eq. (29). We find

$$F(\Lambda) = \Lambda - ae^{-\tau_{RP}\Lambda} + b, \quad (30)$$

which has infinitely many roots $\Lambda \in \mathbb{C}$. Since the characteristic polynomial (30) is a transcendental function, with an infinite number of roots, computing its roots is non-trivial. Hence we use the Lambert W function for solving equations of the form $x = We^W$. By manipulating Eqn. (30) $F(\Lambda) = 0$ into a form that matches this pattern, the Lambert W function can be used to solve for Λ . Rearranging to get

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda &= ae^{-\tau_{RP}\Lambda} - b, \\ \implies \tau_{RP}(\Lambda + b)e^{\tau_{RP}(\Lambda + b)} &= a\tau_{RP}e^{b\tau_{RP}}, \\ \implies \Lambda &= \frac{1}{\tau_{RP}}W(a\tau_{RP}e^{b\tau_{RP}}) - b \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

However, the system's long-term behaviour will be dominated by the eigenvalue Λ_i with the largest real part, here denoted by λ_+ . Since Eq. (29) defines a strongly positive linear dynamical system (*i.e.*, its solution remains strictly positive given a positive initial data), this implies that the dominant eigenvalue λ_+ is real and simple. Hence, we can focus only on studying the real roots of F . As summarized in Lemma 3, the function F has a single real root and this is positive whenever $a > b$ (or equivalently $e^{\alpha\tau_P - U(\tau_P)} > 1$). Biologically this corresponds to cells being more likely to proliferate than die during their transition in the n_P compartment (*i.e.*, during their proliferative state).

Lemma 3. *Given $\tau_{RP} > \tau_P > 0$, $\beta_{\Pi \rightarrow P} > 0$, the function F defined by Eq. (30), with $a := e^{\alpha\tau_P - U(\tau_P)}\beta_{\Pi \rightarrow P}$ and $b := \beta_{\Pi \rightarrow P}$, has a unique real root $\lambda_+ \in \mathbb{R}$ which satisfies*

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_+ > 0, & a > b > 0, \\ \lambda_+ \leq 0, & 0 < a \leq b. \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

Proof. It is obvious that F admits at least a real solution $\lambda_+ \in \mathbb{R}$ as it is a continuous function and $\lim_{\lambda_+ \rightarrow \pm\infty} F(\lambda_+) = \pm\infty$. The uniqueness of the real root of F follows from its monotonicity:

$$\frac{dF}{d\lambda}(\lambda_+) = 1 + a\tau_{RP}e^{-\tau_{RP}\lambda_+} > 0, \quad \forall \lambda_+ \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (33)$$

The sign of λ_+ is connected to the sign of $F(0) = -a + b$. If $F(0) \geq 0$, $F(\lambda) > 0$ for all $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, $\lambda > 0$ and therefore λ_+ will be negative. In contrast, if $F(0) < 0$, then, since $F(+\infty) = +\infty$ and F is strictly monotonically increasing function, the unique root of F , λ_+ , will have to be positive. \square

Computing the exact value of λ_+ goes beyond our aim. Instead, we focus on the implication of our findings for the long-time behaviour of the total number of proliferative N_P and quiescent N_Q cells in the population which we have previously defined in Eq. (28).

3.4 A mechanistic two-compartment tumour growth model

We start by deriving the governing equations for $N_P(t)$ and $N_Q(t)$, differentiating with respect to time Eqs. (28) and using Eqs. (16a)-(16b) we obtain

$$\frac{dN_P}{dt} = -V_P[n_P(x_{max}, t) - n_P(0, t)] + \alpha N_P - \int_0^{x_{max}} \mu(x)n_P(x, t)dx, \quad (34a)$$

$$\frac{dN_Q}{dt} = V_R n_Q^{(I)}(x_{max}, t) - \beta_{II \rightarrow P} N_Q^{(II)}(t). \quad (34b)$$

Substituting the definition of n_P and $n_Q^{(I)}$ in Eqs. (21) and (26) for times $t > \tau_{RP}$, we can rewrite Eq. (34) as

$$\frac{dN_P}{dt} = (\alpha - \bar{\mu}(t))N_P + \beta_{II \rightarrow P}[N_Q^{(II)}(t) - N_Q^{(II)}(t - \tau_P)e^{\alpha\tau_P - U(\tau_P)}], \quad (35a)$$

$$\frac{dN_Q}{dt} = -\beta_{II \rightarrow P}[N_Q^{(II)}(t) - N_Q^{(II)}(t - \tau_P)e^{\alpha\tau_P - U(\tau_P)}], \quad (35b)$$

where we denote the average death rate $\bar{\mu}(t)$

$$\bar{\mu}(t) = \frac{\int_0^{x_{max}} \mu(x)n_P(x, t)dx}{N_P(t)} = \frac{\beta_{II \rightarrow P}}{N_P}(\Phi * N_Q^{(II)}), \quad (36)$$

where the term $\Phi * N_Q^{(II)} = \int_0^{\tau_P} \Phi(T)N_Q^{(II)}(t - T)dT$ indicates the convolution of the function $N_Q^{(II)}$ with the kernel Φ defined as

$$\Phi(T) = \mu(TV_P) \exp[\alpha T - U(T)]. \quad (37)$$

By defining the following parameters:

$$\mu_P = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \bar{\mu}(t), \quad (38a)$$

$$\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \beta_{II \rightarrow P} \frac{N_Q^{(II)}(t)}{N_Q(t)}, \quad (38b)$$

$$\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \beta_{II \rightarrow P} \frac{N_Q^{(II)}(t - \tau_P)e^{\alpha\tau_P - U(\tau_P)}}{N_P(t)}, \quad (38c)$$

we find that asymptotically Eqs. (35) converge to the two-compartment model of tumour growth we have introduced in Chapter 2; namely:

$$\frac{dN_P}{dt} \approx \alpha N_P - \mu_P N_P - \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} N_P + \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} N_Q, \quad t \gg 1, \quad (39a)$$

$$\frac{dN_Q}{dt} \approx \beta_{P \rightarrow Q} N_P - \beta_{Q \rightarrow P} N_Q, \quad t \gg 1. \quad (39b)$$

However, it is important to note that in writing Eq. (39), we are implicitly assuming that the limits defined in Eqs. (38) are well defined. This is indeed the case and follows from the discussion in the previous section on the exponential asymptotic behaviour of $N_Q^{(II)}$. Substituting into Eqs.(38) the asymptotic solution $N_Q \approx \omega e^{\lambda+t}$, we can derive an explicit form for the two-compartment model as a function of the model parameters in our structured population model (*i.e.*, Eq. (28)). First, we estimate the asymptotic behaviour of N_P and $N_Q^{(I)}$ given that $N_Q^{(II)} \sim \omega_Q^{(II)} e^{\lambda+t}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
N_P(t) &= \int_0^{x_{max}} \beta_{II \rightarrow P} \frac{N_Q^{(II)}(t - \frac{\xi}{V_P})}{V_P} e^{\alpha \frac{\xi}{V_P} - U(\frac{\xi}{V_P})} d\xi, \\
&= \int_0^{\tau_P} \beta_{II \rightarrow P} N_Q^{(II)}(t - T) e^{\alpha T - U(T)} dT, \\
&\approx \beta_{II \rightarrow P} \omega_Q^{(II)} e^{\lambda+t} \int_0^{\tau_P} e^{(\alpha - \lambda_+)T - U(T)} dT
\end{aligned} \tag{40a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
N_Q(t) &= N_Q^{(II)}(t) + \int_0^{x_{max}} \frac{V_P}{V_R} n_P \left(x_{max}, t - \frac{x_{max} - x}{V_R} \right) dx, \\
&= N_Q^{(II)}(t) + \int_0^{\tau_R} \beta_{II \rightarrow P} N_Q^{(II)}(t + T - \tau_{RP}) e^{\alpha \tau_P - U(\tau_P)} dT, \\
&\approx \omega_Q^{(II)} e^{\lambda+t} + \int_0^{\tau_R} \beta_{II \rightarrow P} \omega_Q^{(II)} e^{\lambda + (t + T - \tau_{RP}) + \alpha \tau_P - U(\tau_P)} dx, \\
&= \omega_Q^{(II)} e^{\lambda+t} \left(1 + \beta_{II \rightarrow P} e^{-\lambda_+ \tau_{RP} + \alpha \tau_P - U(\tau_P)} \frac{e^{\lambda_+ \tau_R} - 1}{\lambda_+} \right) \\
&\stackrel{F(\lambda_+) = 0}{=} \frac{\omega_Q^{(II)} e^{\lambda+t}}{\lambda_+} [e^{\lambda_+ \tau_R} (\lambda_+ + \beta_{II \rightarrow P}) - \beta_{II \rightarrow P}].
\end{aligned} \tag{40b}$$

Then substituting Eqs. (40) into the definition of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ and $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ from Eqs. (38) we find that:

$$\beta_{P \rightarrow Q} = \frac{e^{\alpha \tau_P - U(\tau_P) - \lambda_+ \tau_P}}{\int_0^{\tau_P} e^{(\alpha - \lambda_+)T - U(T)} dT}. \tag{41a}$$

$$\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = \frac{\lambda_+ \beta_{II \rightarrow P}}{e^{\lambda_+ \tau_R} (\lambda_+ + \beta_{II \rightarrow P}) - \beta_{II \rightarrow P}}. \tag{41b}$$

Finally, we are left with having to estimate μ_P :

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_P &= \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\beta_{\Pi \rightarrow P}}{N_P} \left(\int_0^{\tau_P} \Phi(T) N_Q^{(\Pi)}(t - T) dT \right) \\ &= \frac{\int_0^{\tau_P} \Phi(T) e^{-\lambda_+ T} dT}{\int_0^{\tau_P} e^{(\alpha - \lambda_+)T - U(T)} dT} \\ &= \frac{\int_0^{\tau_P} \mu(T V_P) e^{\alpha T - U(T) - \lambda_+ T} dT}{\int_0^{\tau_P} e^{(\alpha - \lambda_+)T - U(T)} dT}\end{aligned}$$

Integrating by parts using $u = -e^{-\lambda_+ T + \alpha T}$, $v' = -\mu(V_P T) e^{-U(T)}$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_P &= \frac{-[e^{-\lambda_+ T + \alpha T - U(T)}]_{T=0}^{T=\tau_P} + \int_0^{\tau_P} (\alpha - \lambda_+) e^{-\lambda_+ T + \alpha T - U(T)} dT}{\int_0^{\tau_P} e^{(\alpha - \lambda_+)T - U(T)} dT}, \\ &= \alpha - \lambda_+ + \frac{1 - e^{-\lambda_+ \tau_P + \alpha \tau_P - U(\tau_P)}}{\int_0^{\tau_P} e^{(\alpha - \lambda_+)T - U(T)} dT}.\end{aligned}\tag{41c}$$

Looking at Eqns. (41), it is not apparent the specific relation between $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$, $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ and μ_P . This is also due to the dependency of the non-linear relationship between the growth rate λ_+ and the damage-structured model parameters that are set by the characteristic equation $F(\lambda_+) = 0$. Nonetheless, our derivation uncovers the complex dependencies between the different model parameters, including between $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ and $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ that we have not taken into account when considering survival-proliferation trade-offs within the simple modelling framework developed in Chapter 2.

3.5 Emergence of proliferation-survival trade-offs

In Section 2.1, we have naively introduced proliferation-survival trade-offs in our two-compartment model by prescribing the death rate of proliferation cells μ_P as a decreasing function of the transition rate of proliferative cells into quiescence $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$. This choice phenomenologically captured the fact that the more time proliferative cells wait to enter quiescence, the more damage they accumulate and the more likely they are to die. In our structured-population model, the link between delayed quiescent and increased rate of cell death naturally emerges as we have accounted for cell damage, and its connection to cell death, explicitly within the model. In particular, larger values of x_{max} , which indicates the level of damage at which cells enter quiescence, correspond to cells postponing damage repair to favour rapid proliferation; however, larger values also yield an increase in the death rate of cells

Figure 10: Plots illustrating the relations between effective model parameters for the two-compartment model (Eqn. (41)) and population growth rate λ_+ (defined as a root of $F(\lambda)$ in Eqn. (30)) as a function of the maximum damage level x_{max} . We compare results for different values of the repair velocity $V_R = \{0.5, 5\}$. Other parameters are set to the values: $V_P = 1$, $\alpha = 1.1$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\mu_0 = 0.1$, $\beta_{II \rightarrow P} = 0.1$. Note that we start from $x_{max} = 0.5$ since the parameter $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ asymptotes to infinity when $x_{max} \rightarrow 0$, which is unrealistic. Also, the y-axis scales differ between the plots.

(as $\mu' > 0$ and equivalently $U'' > 0$). Since the effective formula for the parameters in Eqs. (41) are consistently derived from our structured-population model, we expect these to also capture proliferation-survival trade-offs. We illustrate this by discussing a specific example.

Suppose the death rate $\mu(x)$ is linearly dependent on the damage level x

$$\mu(x) := \mu_0 + \gamma x, \quad (42)$$

where $\mu_0 \geq 0$ and $\gamma > 0$ are constants. Here γ represents the strength to which damage increases cell death, while μ_0 acts as a natural rate of cell death even in the absence of damage. By substituting our explicit form for $\mu(x)$ (Eqn. (42)) into the definition of $U(\tau_P)$, we find

$$U(\tau_P) = \int_0^{\tau_P} \mu(V_P T) dT = \mu_0 \tau_P + \frac{1}{2} \gamma V_P \tau_P^2. \quad (43)$$

For consistency, we set parameters' values similar to the values used in Chapter 2. The exact numerical values we used are listed in the caption of Figure 10. To study how the effective parameters $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$, $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ and μ_P depend on x_{max} , we first solve for λ_+ numerically in MATLAB using 'lambertw' function and use the estimates to evaluate Eq. (41). Integrals in Eq. (41) are then approximated using the 'integral' function in MATLAB. Results are shown in Fig. 10, where we compare parameter estimates for two different values of the rate of damage repair V_R .

Looking at Figure 10a, the transition rate from proliferation to quiescence ($\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$) is significantly higher at lower maximum damage levels (x_{max}), decreasing as x_{max} increases. This suggests an initially strong but plateauing sensitivity to damage at higher levels. Conversely, the mortality rate of proliferative cells (μ_P) consistently increases with rising x_{max} , as shown in Figure 10c. This aligns with the expectation that increased damage levels lead to higher cancer cell mortality. Given the monotonic decrease of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ with increasing x_{max} , a corresponding decrease in μ_P is observed. This correlation supports the assumptions of the phenomenological proliferation-survival model discussed in Chapter 2 (see Figure 11). Notably, Figure 10b reveals the dependency of the transition from quiescence to proliferation ($\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$) on x_{max} , a factor not considered in our initial model. Specifically, $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ shows a non-linear relationship with x_{max} : decreasing to a minimum before returning asymptotically to its maximal value of $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P} = 0.1$. Despite differences between our mechanistic and phenomenological models, both predict a similar trend in the fitness function λ_+ (compare Figure 10d and Figure 5), which exhibits a distinct global maximum as a function of x_{max} or $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$.

Our phenomenological model interestingly predicts that cells in hypoxia evolve towards lower $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ compared to those in normoxia, indicating a delayed entrance to quiescence (refer to Section 2.6). However, considering the additional factors incorporated in our mechanistic model, we re-evaluate the impact of hypoxia on the proliferation-survival trade-offs and cellular adaptation (see Section 2.5). Figure 10 also incorporates the influence of hypoxia (low oxygen levels) on DNA repair

by assuming reduced DNA repair rates (V_R). Notably, variations in V_R affect not only $\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$ but also influence $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ and μ_P , an aspect our initial phenomenological model overlooked. The fitness function λ_+ 's maxima locations (illustrated in Figure 10d) are influenced by oxygen levels. We observe an increase in the optimal x_{max} with higher oxygen levels, implying a decrease in the optimal $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ under these conditions. Thus, the model suggests that hypoxic cells adapt by evolving towards higher $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ values, indicating an anticipated entrance to quiescence. This finding aligns with our expectations and demonstrates that the unexpected conclusions drawn from the phenomenological model are more reflective of its simplistic assumptions than of novel biological insights.

4 Conclusion

The presence of small subpopulations of quiescent cancer cells is often associated with treatment failure. There is therefore the need to understand what are the mechanisms that drive cancer cells to arrest proliferation and enter in the protective quiescent state. In normal cells, quiescence is activated upon accumulation of damage and it allows time for cells to repair. It has therefore been proposed quiescence in cancer is a survival strategy for cells to persist in hostile environments such as hypoxia (*i.e.*, pathologically low oxygen levels). In this thesis, we used mathematical modelling techniques to investigate the role that survival-proliferation trade-offs play in allowing for the coexistence of proliferative and quiescent cells within the same tumour.

While previous theoretical studies have proposed the role of survival-proliferation trade-offs in shaping the evolution of cancer cells [1], there are no quantitative studies that have tested this hypothesis. In Chapter 2, we propose a simple two-compartment model of tumour growth that accounts for the coexistence of proliferative and quiescent cells. As summarized in Figure 11, in this framework, proliferation-survival tradeoffs are introduced phenomenologically by prescribing a relation between the death rate of proliferative cells (μ_P) and the rate at which cells transition to quiescence ($\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$). By studying the optimal values of $\beta_{P \rightarrow Q}$ for maximising cell fitness, we gain insights into how evolution may shape cancer-cell regulation of entrance to quiescence. We further investigate how survival-proliferation trade-offs affect evolution in different oxygen environments by modelling the dysregulation of damage repair in hypoxia as a decrease in the rate at which cells leave quiescence ($\beta_{Q \rightarrow P}$). While our results can explain the accumulation of quiescent cells in hypoxia, **they also suggest that cells in the hypoxia region evolve to remain in a proliferative state for longer periods.**

In Chapter 3, we present a three-compartment structured-population model of tumour growth that accounts for proliferative and quiescent cells and further captures the regulation of cell damage. While damage is accumulated in proliferative cells, this is repaired in the quiescent compartment. In this framework, trade-offs do not have to be included phenomenological but rather emerge by the detailed description of proliferation/survival mechanisms. We first reduce the structured population model to a system of delay differential and algebraic equations. At long times, we find that this system asymptotes to what we call a mechanistic two-compartment model of tumour growth under proliferation-survival tradeoffs. This is analogous to the model we have previously proposed in Chapter 2, but where the relations between model parameters are consistently derived from a description of intracellular damage dynamics and quiescence regulation rather than

Figure 11: Summary schematic comparing how different biological mechanisms of interest are accounted for in the phenomenological two-compartment model from Chapter 2 and the mechanistic two-compartment model derived from the damage structured-population model described in Section 3.1.

phenomenologically imposed (see Figure 11). We use this refined model to study how evolution shapes how cancer cells regulate entrance to quiescence in different oxygen environments. Our preliminary results suggest that oxygen affects the regulation of quiescence in cancer cells by favouring early entrance to quiescence in hypoxia. This is in contrast to the conclusion we have drawn in Chapter 2, suggesting that our phenomenological description of survival/proliferation trade-offs was originally too simplistic. An extension of this work is the analysis of predictions of the mechanistic two-compartment model derived by combining analytical and numerical results as done in Section 2.5. This could provide a more detailed explanation of how cells adapt quiescence under hypoxia conditions.

In the future, it would be interesting to extend our model to account for treatment, for example, radiotherapy, which uses high-energy electromagnetic waves or particles to cause damage to cellular DNA, resulting in cell death [15]. Besides offering insights into the dynamic regulation of damage during treatment, such a model could be used to investigate to which extent the different regulation of quiescence in hypoxic cancer cells contributes to their radioresistance.

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